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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The two most advanced instrument concepts for the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) work together and both have substantial Canadian participation: The Narrow Field Infrared Adaptive Optics System (NFIRAOS) is the first-light facility Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) system and is led by NRC Herzberg Astronomy and Astrophysics (HAA). The InfraRed Imaging Spectrograph (IRIS) is the first client instrument of NFIRAOS. The IRIS team is drawn from the University of California system, CIT, NAOJ, TMT, and NRC HAA.

NFIRAOS will provide diffraction-limited performance in J, H, and K bands over a wide field. NFIRAOS will deliver images that will be the sharpest of any existing facility AO system. For astronomers to be fully satisfied with TMT + NFIRAOS + IRIS, they must be able to observe their key science programs. The laser guide stars, the use of MCAO, and on-instrument near-infrared wavefront sensors (OIWFSs) all contribute to achieving diffraction-limited performance 50% of the time at the North Galactic Pole. NRC HAA and its Canadian industrial contractors successfully passed the NFIRAOS final design review in June 2018.

IRIS will use 4 mas pixels across a 34x34 arcsecond field of view. It will contain up to 60 broad and narrow-band filters that span wavelengths from 0.8 to 2.4 microns. IRIS contains two selectable Integral Field Spectrographs with varying spectral resolutions and platescales. NRC is responsible for the thermal and mechanical interfaces to NFIRAOS, as well as providing the rotator and OIWFSs. IRIS is scheduled to complete its final design review in early 2021.

We present an overview of the key elements of the NFIRAOS and IRIS designs and highlight some of the important performance budgets and design solutions made along the way. We discuss the challenges and rewards of working with industry on large, complex instrumentation projects. We invite more Canadian participation in the science teams for these first light workhorse TMT instruments. Lessons learned from these instruments will be important as the 2nd generation of TMT instruments are planned.

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TMT was listed as the “single most important project, in the near term, for Canadian astronomy” in the 2010 Long Range Plan. On April 6, 2015, Canadian Prime Minister Stephen Harper announced that his government would commit \$243.5 million to the TMT project. This commitment would cover in-kind work packages to have Canada build the TMT enclosure (dome), the first-light Adaptive Optics (AO) system for TMT, NFIRAOS (Narrow Field Infrared Adaptive Optics System; Herriot et al. (2014); Crane et al. (2018)), and be a major partner in the NFIRAOS client instrument IRIS (InfraRed Imaging Spectrograph; Larkin et al. (2016)), in addition to some cash contributions to the observatory. As 2019 comes to a close, NFIRAOS has completed its Final Design Review (FDR) and is preparing to enter its fabrication phase. IRIS is more than halfway through its Final Design Phase and will have its FDR in early 2021. The Canadian work related to NFIRAOS and IRIS has been a major contribution to the TMT project. NFIRAOS and IRIS will continue to be major projects for NRC HAA and its industrial and academic partners throughout the next decade; they may be the only instruments available at first light (which will hopefully be achieved before 2030). In this white paper, we review the requirements and current design of NFIRAOS and IRIS to highlight some of the science that will be made possible by Canada’s initial contribution to TMT.

Figure 1: Rendering of NFIRAOS (in blue) on the TMT Nasmyth platform. IRIS (in grey) is mounted below NFIRAOS.

1 NFIRAOS

NFIRAOS is an ambitious Multi-Conjugate AO (MCAO) system that will be ready by first light of TMT (Figure 1). After the Treasury Board awarded money to TMT, NRC HAA subdivided NFIRAOS into subsystems and subcontracted the final design of these subsystems to Canadian industry. The project has now engaged six Canadian industrial partners to develop the final design of eight major NFIRAOS subsystems. Working with industry to develop designs to specifications was a new approach for the NRC team, and NFIRAOS has benefited greatly from these companies' expertise.

NFIRAOS itself will provide diffraction-limited performance in the J, H, and K bands (enabling science at wavelengths between 0.8 and 2.4 μm over 34 arcsec diameter fields with 50% sky coverage at the Galactic Pole. By virtue of its size and the excellent AO correction courtesy of NFIRAOS, TMT will yield extraordinarily high spatial resolution in the near-infrared (see Figure 2). Years of effort have been spent to ensure that TMT and NFIRAOS deliver images that on average will be the sharpest of any existing facility AO system; NFIRAOS is required to deliver Strehl ratios of greater than 50% in H-band in median conditions (Herriot et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2018). Sky coverage is, of course, also a key performance metric. For astronomers to be fully satisfied with TMT + NFIRAOS + IRIS, they must be able to observe their key science programs. Six laser guide stars (LGS), the use of MCAO, and the on-instrument near-infrared tip/tilt/focus sensors (OIWFSs) all contribute to achieving diffraction-limited performance 50% of the time at the North Galactic Pole (Andersen et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2014). This sky coverage fraction increases dramatically for fields closer to the galactic plane where many more stars are available.

Figure 2: Comparison of diffraction-limited images taken with Keck Observatory AO versus the expected performance of NFIRAOS and IRIS. This simulation shows the center of our Milky Way galaxy. A 4 million solar mass black hole resides at the location of the radio source Sagittarius A*. By monitoring stars orbiting around the black hole, TMT astronomers will be able to test the predictions of General Relativity. (Credit: T. Do, IRIS science team)

The NFIRAOS functionality and performance has been captured in roughly 400 detailed requirements that have been driven by numerous performance budgets and studies. Many of the NFIRAOS design decisions were made to maximize point source sensitivity. A few examples of these design choices include: cooling NFIRAOS to -30°C to minimize the thermal background (Andersen et al., 2010) and to set tight limits on the pupil alignment budget (undersizing the cold Lyot stop in IRIS throws light away and broadens the diffraction pattern). The TMT and NFIRAOS and IRIS teams have also invested in understanding and minimizing photometric and astrometric errors (Schöck et al., 2014). One major implication of these studies was that it was recognized that astrometry would be compromised in the presence of a rotating distortion field. The NFIRAOS optical relay was redesigned using four

off-axis parabolas (OAPs) to minimize both wavefront error and distortion from NFIRAOS thus enabling $50 \mu\text{s}$ precision astrometry for $H < 20$ stars in less than 100 seconds (with a noise floor of $10 \mu\text{s}$). Another area of great focus for TMT in general, and NFIRAOS and IRIS in particular, is understanding and minimizing observing overheads. The complete target acquisition, involving the slewing of the telescope, propagation of the laser guide stars, closing the AO loops, and confirmation of the target field, is required to be complete in less than 5 minutes.

The design of NFIRAOS has evolved to meet these requirements (Figure 3). Telescope light enters NFIRAOS through its entrance window and then passes by the deployable NFIRAOS source simulator, which comprises two units: the six Laser Guide Star (LGS) sources; and the Natural Guide Star (NGS) source and focal-plane mask. Light is then further relayed off three OAPs and the two deformable mirrors (DMs) which are controlled by the Real-Time Controller (RTC; Kerley et al. (2016)). These two DMs are optically conjugate to 0 m (ground) and 11 km above TMT. They are appropriately labeled DM0 and DM11 in the figure below. These 2 DMs, working in series in a MCAO system can effectively correct for a greater volume of atmospheric turbulence which dramatically increases the field of correction for NFIRAOS. DM0 is mounted in a large Tip-Tilt stage (TTS) that can be used to compensate for atmospheric tip-tilt, windshake and vibration. A science beamsplitter transmits long-wavelength light to the infrared science-instrument path and reflects shorter-wavelength visible light to the LGS and NGS WFS paths. At the end of the science path, a final OAP refocuses the light, and the instrument selection mirror directs it to one of three instrument ports. The visible light reflected by the beamsplitter is split into the visible light (600-800 nm) and the narrow-band laser light (589 nm) by a second beamsplitter. The laser light is re-imaged by its own private copy of the final OAP mirror and directed into the LGS WFS subsystem. The six LGS WFS detectors stream pixels to the RTC to drive the DMs and tip/tilt stage. Visible light from an NGS is refocused by another copy of the final OAP and sent to the visible NGS WFS labelled as a Pyramid WFS below. This WFS can be used when LGS are unavailable or can act as a slow truth or fast tip-tilt NGS WFS in MCAO mode.

Figure 3: Isometric view of NFIRAOS optics

NFIRAOS has been under development since 2004; TMT recognized that building a telescope capable of delivering the best diffraction-limited performance possible required a dedicated team of engineers and AO scientists working on an AO instrument that would be capable of helping guide observatory design choices. The core team at NRC and TMT that started that work on NFIRAOS is still in place. The institutional memory of this team has

enabled NFIRAOS to keep moving forward and prevented important design considerations from being forgotten or over-looked. NFIRAOS completed its FDR in June, 2018. The team now is continuing with some remaining design and analysis work while we wait for TMT construction to commence. When TMT breaks ground, NRC HAA will kick off its fabrication phase and re-engage with our Canadian industry partners to fabricate, assemble and test individual NFIRAOS subsystems. NRC is already actively building an integration facility in Victoria that can be used to assemble, integrate and test TMT instruments, including NFIRAOS and IRIS. As Canadian industry delivers NFIRAOS subsystems to Victoria, NFIRAOS will be assembled. We will be able to test and verify most the NFIRAOS requirements in Victoria before it is disassembled and shipped to TMT for integration with the telescope.

2 IRIS

IRIS is a cryogenic instrument under development for first-light operation of TMT and is a client instrument of NFIRAOS. IRIS combines a “wide-field” imager with an integral field spectrograph (IFS) and is sensitive to wavelengths in the range of 0.84 μm to 2.4 μm . The IRIS Imager uses four Hawaii-4RG-10 detectors, which yield a total field-of-view (FoV) of 34×34 arcsec at a platescale of 4 mas. The IFS offers four spaxel scales ranging from 4 mas to 50 mas, and is capable of generating up to 14,000 simultaneous spectra within a filled rectangular pattern. The Imager and IFS are encased by the science cryostat, which provides the light-tight, cryogenic vacuum environment required by the Imager and IFS subsystems. Three on-instrument wavefront sensors (OIWFS) are mounted in a separate enclosure atop the science cryostat; these patrol the exterior perimeter of the two arcminute diameter field delivered by NFIRAOS and provide measurements of the tip/tilt, focus (TTF) and plate scale modes invisible to NFIRAOS and its LGS WFS. The OIWFS enclosure provides mechanical and thermal interfaces to NFIRAOS. IRIS also mates to NFIRAOS through a support structure, which in turn interfaces to a rotator bearing that serves as the interface to both the OIWFS enclosure and science cryostat. The rotator enables IRIS to provide its own field de-rotation. The final component of IRIS is the services cable wrap, which routes the cables from the OIWFS and science cryostat to the Nasmyth platform below the instrument and out to either the IRIS electronics cabinet or the TMT facility supplied services. A rendering of IRIS placed underneath NFIRAOS within the observatory is shown in Figure 4.

The IRIS team is an international collaboration. The project PI is James Larkin (UCLA), the Project Manager is Eric Chisholm (TMT) and the Project Scientist is Shelley Wright (UCSD). NAOJ is leading the development of the Imager. CIT is designing the science and OIWFS cryostats and the slicer IFS option. UC is designing the lenslet IFS option and taking care of the electronics and data reduction software. Canada is responsible for the support structure, the rotator bearing, OIWFS arms and enclosure, and the cable wrap as well as leading the overall software development effort.

The ‘raison d’être’ of IRIS is to provide the means to enable cutting-edge research for its user base (Wright et al., 2016). Since 2008, an international science team has helped shape the scientific priorities and performance requirements for IRIS. The science team members have been steadfast in refining IRIS’s capabilities, including the counselling of trade-studies through which they have developed a strong synergy with the design team. The result of this ‘team’ effort has helped advance the technical design. The IRIS science cases, which have driven the IRIS design requirements, can be found on-line (https://oirlab.ucsd.edu/IRIS_science.html). IRIS’s science ambitions are broad, covering all distance scales and spanning fields of astronomical research as varied as solar system science to first light galaxies. Each case clearly presents the critical links to the IRIS design requirements as formalized in the IRIS Design Requirements Document. The science team is still open to membership from TMT partners to anyone interested in exploiting this powerful imaging spectrograph.

To illustrate the potential and beauty of IRIS consider the following specific example. IRIS has a range of science cases that drive the imager towards a larger FoV and simultaneous 3D spectroscopy using the finest and coarsest spatial scales of the IFS. One of the leading science cases for IRIS is to study the Galactic Center with unprecedented sensitivity and spatial resolution. If we achieve our goal of relative astrometric accuracy of better than $30 \mu\text{as}$, we will be able to test General Relativity and probe the distribution of dark matter through orbital

Figure 4: The IRIS instrument shown in-situ mounted to the up-looking port of NFIRAOS. The silver cylinder in the lower portion of the image is the IRIS cable services wrap, which is designed to prevent damage to IRIS cables as the cryostat rotates during operations. For scale, the blue dewar is 1.9 meters in diameter.

monitoring of the stars surrounding Sgr A* (Figure 2). Using the IRIS expanded imager capability ($34'' \times 34''$) we will be able to observe the crucial astrometric maser sources in a single observation, which will greatly improve the astrometric accuracy in this field. This is imperative for measuring the orbits of the inner-arcsecond sources surrounding Sgr A* and exploring the fundamental physics of the SMBH. The expanded IRIS imager will also allow greater accessibility and ease of studying the stellar population at the Galactic Center. This is just one use of the expanded imager FoV science case. The science cases for IRIS are divided into the following areas:

- First light sources ($z > 8$)
- The characterizations of high-redshift galaxies ($1 < z < 5$)
- Gravitational-lensing galaxies: dark matter and dark energy (Figure 5)
- Characterization of supermassive black holes and active galactic nuclei
- Stellar populations and characterization of local galaxies
- Star formation histories of dwarf galaxies
- Dynamics and stellar populations in the Galactic center
- Star formation in the Local Group
- Stellar evolution using astrometric microlensing
- The formation and characterization of exoplanets
- Active Solar System bodies and history of the solar system

IRIS is midway through its final design phase in late 2019. It is on-track to complete the FDR by early 2021. It is a large, complex instrument, but is on pace to be complete for TMT first light at the end of the 2020's. It is possible that NFIRAOS and IRIS will be the only first light instruments at TMT depending on the progress of other instrument designs. They will make a powerful combination that will serve the Canadian astronomical community well. NRC HAA will continue to lead the design and fabrication of a substantial fraction of IRIS. IRIS will first come together as a complete instrument in Victoria, and will be integrated and tested with NFIRAOS before moving to TMT. Together, NFIRAOS and the Canadian contribution to IRIS will represent a substantial

Figure 5: IRIS simulation of a distant strong gravitationally-lensed galaxy. (LEFT) Original ALMA 1.0 mm image of the gravitationally-lensed galaxy SDP.81 at $z = 3.042$ with 23 mas resolution used for Keck/NIRC2 and TMT/IRIS simulations.

portion of the in-kind Canadian contribution to the TMT.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

NFIRAOS and IRIS are first-light work-horse instruments for TMT that work together to take full advantage of the diffraction limit and light gathering power of a 30m aperture. NFIRAOS and IRIS will have a resolution limit of 15 mas in H-band, and is being designed to measure accurate positions of stars to better than $30 \mu\text{s}$. Not only will NFIRAOS and IRIS be used to study more and fainter stars orbiting closer to the Black Hole in the Milky Way to probe the fundamental gravitational physics in this environment, this level of astrometric accuracy even for stars as faint as $H < 20$ in 100 sec exposures will open up whole new avenues of astrometric studies where it may seem that everything moves. We will be able to measure the movement of stars in nearby extragalactic targets to take methods long used to study the kinematics of our Galaxy to M31 and beyond. IRIS will both be able to perform imaging over a 34×34 square arcsecond field of view and integral field spectroscopy over a roughly 2×2 square arcsecond field simultaneously. There are multiple resolutions and IFU plate scales available to perform spectroscopy with resolutions between 4000 and 8000. As laid out in the summary of the science cases above, TMT+NFIRAOS+IRIS will be used to observe everything from solar system objects to first light sources at $z > 8$. In short, NFIRAOS and IRIS will be a workhorse for TMT that will be used perhaps every night during the first years of operations of the observatory.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

NFIRAOS has been designed to achieve better than 50% Strehl ratio in H-band in median conditions with 50% sky coverage at the North Galactic Pole. This is an ambitious goal that has not yet been achieved by other wide-field AO systems. Sky coverage will be achieved by using stars as faint as $J < 22$. This is possible because the IRIS OIWSF will take advantage of the high order AO sharpening provided by NFIRAOS. The scientific risk is that TMT, NFIRAOS and IRIS will not be able to meet these requirements, particularly in the early days of the TMT observatory. Many complex systems will have to all meet their requirements. The TMT, NFIRAOS and IRIS systems engineering teams have spent years developing performance budgets to understand sources of error. The NRC HAA team, in particular, has put a focus on understanding and mitigating sources of vibration in the telescope and its instruments. Even if NFIRAOS and IRIS do not achieve 50% Strehl ratio in H-band at first light, there are requirement verification plans in place to ensure that the observatory meets

these requirements eventually.

Another, perhaps unexpected, scientific risk for NFIRAOS and IRIS is saturation. Combining the collecting power of a 30 m telescope with high performance and high throughput AO system and instrument means that even stars that are considered faint with $H < 17$ could saturate in broadband images in minimum exposure times on the H4RG detectors of the IRIS imager. Saturation will lead to persistence on the detector which will affect observations for hours afterwards. IRIS will contain roughly 50 filters, and narrow-band filters and even neutral density filters will be useful for avoiding saturation up to a point for some science cases. The IRIS team has also recently added a shutter to the Imager that will allow long exposures on the IFS while blocking light to the Imager. Finally, the team is researching windows on HxRG detectors to understand how multiple windows performing fast readouts on subwindows centered on the brightest stars can prevent saturation.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canada is already heavily invested in both NFIRAOS and IRIS. NFIRAOS, in fact, is the only TMT instrument to date that is undertaken by a single country. Canada provides the management, the technical expertise, and input into the science to be performed with NFIRAOS. The NFIRAOS team at NRC HAA is leading the effort, with support from our Canadian industrial partners.

IRIS is being designed as part of a multi-national collaboration in which Canada has always taken on a major role. Three Canadian astronomers are involved in the IRIS science team. At one time, Shelley Wright was the project scientist for IRIS based out of the University of Toronto before she moved to UC San Diego. There is still an opportunity to be involved with the IRIS science team which will enable more Canadian astronomers to be fully prepared to make the best use of this amazing instrument when it gets on sky.

NRC HAA has taken on a large technical role in the project. The OIWFS, its enclosure, the rotator bearing, support structure and cable wrap are all part of the Canadian work package. All of these subsystems are being designed and will eventually be built in Canada by NRC HAA. Canada has also been leading the software development effort for the full IRIS instrument.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

There is obvious support and interest in TMT from the Canadian astronomical community as expressed in the LRP 2010. The CASCA/ACURA TMT Advisory Committee (CATAC) has engaged the Canadian community in dialogue related to TMT. An excellent opportunity to become directly involved in NFIRAOS and IRIS is to join the IRIS science team, led by Shelley Wright at UC San Diego. Any astronomer willing to perform simulations and evaluate what science they can achieve with NFIRAOS and IRIS will be welcome. Science team members will receive advice and tools to bring to bear on new science cases. We welcome new input, since science has driven many design choices over time. Creative astronomers will find that the operational flexibility of NFIRAOS and IRIS offer many interesting modes that have not yet been exploited by other science team members.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

As discussed, NFIRAOS and IRIS will be workhorse instruments in 2030 and beyond and will be heavily used by Canadian astronomers. The major involvement of Canada in both NFIRAOS and IRIS will also help pave the way for future TMT instruments. The NRC HAA team that has been involved in these projects has worked with TMT to develop and refine the processes used for instrumentation development within the TMT observatory. These lessons will benefit all future project work with TMT. With the success of the

NFIRAOS and IRIS teams as they proceed through the design stages, NRC HAA and Canada have been developing a reputation as good partners who produce quality work to the benefit of the observatory. Already, instrument teams planning for the next generation of TMT instruments have been looking to involve Canada and NRC HAA. This interest will benefit Canadian astronomers who can help define future instruments both scientifically and technically from their initial concepts.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

NFIRAOS and a significant fraction of IRIS make up a sizable portion of the in-kind Canadian contribution to the construction of TMT. Canadian astronomers, therefore, will receive some fraction of TMT observing time just from the completion of these critical first light instruments. As long as TMT remains a high priority for the Canadian astronomical community, the money and resources spent to deliver the work horse, 1st light instrumentation will be worthwhile.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

Obviously, the issues surrounding the TMT site are a major programmatic risk for NFIRAOS and IRIS, but is outside the scope of this paper. The design teams have been proceeding with their work so that when TMT is built, NFIRAOS and IRIS will be available at first light.

The other major programmatic risks identified here have elements that serve as threats to the projects and elements that serve as opportunities.

The NFIRAOS project is very involved with Canadian industry. In terms of threats, working with industry has a risk of generating large cost overruns that can occur quickly when teams of industry engineers are actively working and questions or changes to scope and requirements emerge. NRC HAA mitigate this risk by carefully defining the requirements, interfaces and scope of subsystems before letting any subcontracts. Once contracts are in place, significant resources are devoted to monitoring the progress of the industry partners and being in frequent communication. On the positive side, engaging with industry on NFIRAOS is a real opportunity to involve groups of technical experts with fresh eyes capable of producing improved designs on short timescales. Our industrial partners bring expertise in fields like structural engineering and refrigeration that are not areas of specialization at NRC HAA.

One of the biggest risks for the IRIS project comes from working as part of a large, international collaboration. Threats to IRIS have emerged because it is difficult to manage independent groups across many partners. Every group brings different outlooks, concerns, and institutional interests to the project. Communication adds overhead, but is critical for keeping groups focused on progress and mitigating this threat. The opportunities to build closer ties across national boundaries are enormous, however. The bonds between team members that have been working together closely for years increases the likelihood of future partnerships, especially, but not limited to, TMT. In the future, it will remain difficult for any single partner to have sufficient resources, technical ability, and money to develop TMT instruments, so international instrument teams will become the norm.

ELT instruments are large, complex and costly. There are already several examples of ELT instruments that have stalled in development or had the partnerships change radically during the design process. NFIRAOS and IRIS have weathered these threats. NFIRAOS passed its Final Design Review in 2018, and IRIS is proceeding through the Final Design Phase now.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

NFIRAOS and IRIS have already benefited Canadians through industrial opportunities and HQP training. NFIRAOS has issued subcontracts for eight subsystems to date to six Canadian firms: Accent Refrigeration Systems; ABB Bomem; Dynamic Structures; Institut national d'optique – INO; Quantum Technology; Sightline Engineering. NRC HAA manages the subcontracts and HAA systems engineering defines the requirements and interfaces of individual subsystems. The industry partners have successfully designed these subsystems to requirement, and will soon begin the fabrication phase where they will fabricate, assemble and test individual subsystems that will undergo acceptance testing by NRC HAA before being shipped to Victoria and integrated at NRC HAA. This model of industrial engagement may have to become more common for future projects if Canada plans on leading and taking the majority of the work for future TMT instruments. Industry has learned the level of effort and systems engineering required to bring a ground-based instrument design to final design. Accent, Quantum Technology and INO have become involved in other projects for TMT and even the Giant Magellan Telescope through their experience working on NFIRAOS. NRC has learned how to efficiently engage with industry on design work, which will increase the capacity of the NRC HAA instrument group. Finally, having Canadian industry more involved in ground-based instrumentation will benefit all instrument groups in Canada in terms of being able to provide engineering support to increasingly complex projects.

The NRC NFIRAOS and IRIS teams are not mandated to develop HQP, but both projects have benefited significantly through the involvement of co-op students, graduate students, and post docs. Developing engineers, in turn, have had exciting opportunities to work on state of the art projects. A partial list of projects performed by students and post docs for NFIRAOS and IRIS include: focal plane wavefront sensing to calibrate non-common path aberrations (Lamb et al., 2014), building a scale version of NFIRAOS in the HAA lab (dubbed HeNOS) to test NFIRAOS Real-Time Control (RTC) algorithms (Mieda et al., 2018), developing advanced control algorithms for the RTC, building and testing a prototype “snout” that serves as the rotating thermal interface between NFIRAOS and IRIS, and studying Galil controller functions to help develop the hardware control daemon. Students and post docs will continue to be involved in these projects as they proceed through fabrication and prepare to be deployed on-sky.

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